

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF 3-D BRAIDED HYBRID METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The concepts of geometric and material hybrids for SiC/Al composites are demonstrated in this study. Tensile, notched beam three-point bending and compact tension tests were conducted in order to study the hybrid effect on 3-D braided composites. The hybrid braided SiC/AL-6061 composites studied include 100% braided Nicalon, 75% braided Nicalon/25% longitudinal lay-in SCS and 50% braided Nicalon/50% longitudinal lay-in SCS. Addition of the strong and stiff SCS filaments to the Nicalon reinforced aluminum strengthens the composites and modifies the composite failure mode from matrix-dominated failure to lay-in yarns-controlled failure. Modelling of the tensile response of the hybrid composites was carried out using the Finite Cell Model (FCM). Good agreement between predictions and experimental results was found.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advantages of improving specific strength, modulus, thermal stability and fatigue resistance through the use of metal matrix composites (MMC) have been well recognized in the past decade. Popular use of MMC hinges upon the development of economical manufacturing processes and the improvement of strength without tremendous sacrifice of toughness. According to DiCarlo [1], the strength of MMC can be improved by the use of continuous fibers bonded strongly to the matrix. In order to improve toughness, fibers having a relatively large diameter, high in-situ strength and low density of critical flaws are recommended. In order to facilitate near net shape manufacturing, a three dimensional fiber architecture capable of assuming various structural shapes is desirable. A wide variety of structural shapes have been demonstrated in our laboratory by the 3-D braiding process [2].

In this study, the concept of geometric and materials hybrids is demonstrated. Combining the flexible Nicalon SiC yarns in a three-dimensional fiber network with strategically placed large diameter, thermally stable SCS-6 SiC filaments in an aluminum matrix, the mechanical properties of the composites were characterized by simple tensile, notched beam three-point bending and compact tension testing. Based on the experimental observations, the tensile properties of the MMC were modelled according to the finite cell methodology. A failure criterion based on the rule-of-mixture was employed to predict the strength of the hybrid composites.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials The material systems used for the study include Nicalon[®] β -SiC, SCS-6 SiC and 6061 aluminum. The SiC fibers were selected because of their wettability and relative thermal stability in comparison to fibers such as boron. The small fiber diameter makes the Nicalon yarn flexible and lends itself to ease of handling and braiding into complex structural shapes. The SCS-6 filaments are only suitable for tape layup or winding over a large radius of curvature because of their high bending rigidity. Accordingly, SCS-6 yarns are used as layin yarns in the 0° direction. A summary of the properties of the fibers and matrix is given in Table 1.

The braiding process has been detailed elsewhere [2]. A 1 x 1 construction was used for all the specimens with a fiber volume fraction of 35% and a surface braiding angle of 20°. Bundles of SCS-6 filaments were distributed evenly as 0° layin filaments to make up a braiding/ layin yarn ratio of 75/25, 50/50 and 25/75, respectively. The 3-D braided preforms were infiltrated with 6061 aluminum by pressure casting at Amercom, Inc. The processing temperature was 770°C at a pressure of 689 MPa for 20 minutes.

B. Testing The MMC specimens were characterized by simple tensile test, three-point bending and compact tension test. Four observations were made in each type of test, and all the tests were carried out at a speed of .5 mm/min.

The dimensions of a tensile test specimen were 20.3 cm long x 2.54 cm wide x .32 cm thick. The specimens were tested to rupture in order to produce an entire stress-strain curve for the MMC.

The fracture behavior of the MMC was characterized by three-point bend testing on a notched beam specimen and by compact tension testing. The notched beam test is aimed at measuring the energy required to initiate a crack, whereas the

compact tension test was intended to assess the energy required to propagate a crack.

The notched beam test was carried out based on the procedure described by Tattersall [3]. Figure 1a shows a schematic of the test setup with a specimen having dimensions of 7.62 cm x .64 cm x .64 cm and a span width of 5 cm. The specimens were loaded until they broke into halves. The fracture surface energy, expressed in KJ/m^2 , is the area under the load-deflection curve.

The compact tension test was carried out according to ASTM test method E399 for plane-strain fracture toughness of metallic materials except that the crack was created by diamond saw cutting rather than by fatigue loading. In order to evaluate the role of the large filaments in stopping crack propagation, the cracks were created along the direction perpendicular to the SCS-6 layin filament. A schematic drawing of the test specimen is shown in Figure 1b, with a specimen thickness of .64 cm. A standard clip gage was used to monitor the crack opening displacement (COD).

III. EXPERIMENTAL OBSERVATIONS

A. Tensile Behavior Figure 2 shows the stress-strain curves of the MMC reflecting the nonlinear behavior of the matrix. In comparison to the pure cast aluminum sample, the 100% braided composites show only a slight reinforcement effect whereas the hybrid composites show a remarkable improvement in strength and toughness as the percentage of longitudinal SCS-6 layin yarns increases. The fiber architecture, as well as the reinforcing material, play a significant role in the failure characteristics of the composites.

Figure 3 shows the schematic of fracture surfaces of the braided hybrid composites. For the 100% braided composites, the fracture surface is fairly smooth. Mostly, when matrix cracks reach the brittle braiding yarns, the yarns are broken without a large change in crack direction. For the 75% braid/25% SCS-6 composite, the fracture surface is rather rough, and fiber pullout is evident. The introduction of strong SCS-6 filaments tends to block the matrix crack propagation and causes the crack to change its original direction. The tensile strength of SCS-6 filaments is higher than the bonding strength between SCS-6 filaments and matrix; therefore, a fiber pull-out failure mode can be observed. For the 50% braid/50% SCS-6 composites, crack deflection and crack bridging phenomena can be observed. Due to the statistical nature of filament fracture, the weakest point of each filament scatters; hence, the matrix crack is greatly deflected.

B. Fracture Behavior

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1. Notched Beam Test The effect of geometric and material hybrids of the MMC with four Nicalon/SCS-6 ratios (100/0,75/25, 50/50 and 25/75) are shown in the schematics depicted in Figure 4. It can be seen that the strong, large diameter SCS-6 filaments tend to dominate the fracture behavior and play a key role in preventing catastrophic failure of the composite. When the propagating crack reaches a bundle of SCS-6 filaments, the crack propagation rate is delayed and gradual failure occurs, as illustrated in the zig-zag pattern of the load-deflection curves. Therefore, when more SCS-6 filaments are introduced, the fracture surface becomes rougher and exhibits more SCS-6 filament pull-out.

In order to further investigate the effect of the proportion of SCS-6 filament, the total energy absorbed during three-point bending was calculated and plotted against the percentage of SCS filaments (Figure 5). It is obvious that the energy required to induce failure increases as the percentage of SCS filaments in the composite increases. This phenomenon owes much to the fracture mechanism by which tensile failure occurs at the tip of the test section followed by tearing in the bottom of the test section. Since the strong SCS-6 filaments sustain the load and delay crack propagation, the fracture energy of the composite is increased.

2. Compact Tension Test The compact tension test provides a measure of the fracture toughness of the composite. The stress-intensity factors for the specimens with notch parallel to the braiding axis are shown in Table 3. The K_q values were calculated from load P_q , determined by drawing a secant line having a slope 5% less than the initial slope of the load-COD curve (in accordance with ASTM E-399). The K_{max} values were based on maximum load, P_{max} , from each loading increment. It can be seen that the fracture toughness of the composite decreases as the percentage of SCS-6 filaments increases.

For braided hybrid specimens with notches along the braiding axis, the crack propagates parallel to the direction of the lay-in SCS-6 filaments and causes splitting of the specimen in the direction of the lay-in yarns. For the 100% braided specimens with notches along the braiding axis, the crack propagates along the braiding angle (θ) and changes direction ($-\theta$) when the crack encounters the interlacing of the braiding yarns. However, the crack changes direction from ($-\theta$) to (θ) when it hits the next interlacing, resulting in a zig-zag appearance within the fracture surface.

For the braided hybrid specimens having notches perpendicular to the braiding axis (following the direction of the laid-in SCS-6 filaments), crack propagates perpendicular to the notch-cutting direction. In this case, the strong SCS-6 filaments stop the crack growth and change a mode-I failure into a mixed-mode failure. As the SCS-6 filaments are much stronger than the interface between the SCS-6 filaments and the matrix, the crack does not rupture the filaments and, instead, runs around the SCS-6 filaments. This manifests the inadequacy of the calculations for K_q . For example, the 100% braided specimens with notching perpendicular to the braiding axis demonstrate crack propagation by tensile fracture of the braiding yarns and shearing of the matrix. On the other hand, the fracture load of the specimens with a notch perpendicular to the braiding axis is higher than that of the corresponding specimens with a notch parallel to the braiding axis.

IV. MODELLING

A. Strength The rule-of-mixture can be applied to predict the ultimate tensile strength of a braided hybrid composite. In the case of the 100% braided composites, where composite failure is dominated by matrix failure, i.e., the Nicalon fibers break as the matrix fails, the ultimate strength of the composite can be expressed by

$$\sigma_{cu} = \sigma_{AL} + \epsilon_{AL} E_{Nicalon} V_{Nicalon} (\cos^2 \theta) \quad (1)$$

where θ = braiding angle = $\tan^{-1}((1+k^2)^{1/2} \tan(\theta_o)/k)$
 k = track/column movement ratio
 θ_o = surface braiding angle.

For the braided hybrid composites, the reinforcing fibers are able to carry the load after matrix failure. Thus, the the ultimate strength of the composites can be estimated in general by the following conditional equation:

$$\sigma_{cu} = \text{MAX} \{ [\sigma_{u1} V_1 (\cos^2 \theta) + (\epsilon_{u1} E_2 V_2) / \cos^2 \theta], \sigma_{u2} V_2 \} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{u1} and σ_{u2} are the strengths of fiber 1 and fiber 2, respectively; V_1 and V_2 are the volume fractions of fiber 1 and fiber 2, respectively; ϵ_{u1} is the ultimate strain of fiber 1, and E_2 is the modulus of the fiber 2. Note that the ultimate strain of fiber 2 is larger than that of fiber 1.

In the case of the 75% braid/25% lay-in composites, where the SCS-6 filaments occupy a relative small volume fraction within the composites, the SCS-6 filaments

can not carry the applied load once the Nicalon fibers break. Thus, the ultimate strength is given by:

$$\sigma_{cu} = \sigma_{Nicalon} V_{Nicalon} (\cos^2 \theta) + (\epsilon_{Nicalon} E_{SCS-6} V_{SCS-6}) / \cos^2 \theta \quad (3)$$

In the case of a 50% braid/50% lay-in composite, the increased amount of SCS-6 filaments are able to take the entire applied load when matrix and braiding yarns fail. Hence, the ultimate strength is as follows:

$$\sigma_{cu} = \sigma_{SCS-6} V_{SCS-6} \quad (4)$$

By substituting the material properties listed in Table 1 into the above equations, the ultimate strengths can be calculated. It can be seen, as shown in Table 2, that the calculated strength agrees well with the experimental data. This indicates that the failure mechanism of the hybrid composite may be similar to the one described in the model.

B. Stress-Strain Relationship The finite cell model (FCM) was used to predict the elastic behavior of the composites. The FCM is based on the concept of fabric unit cell structure and structural analysis. The fiber architecture within the composite is considered as an assemblage of a finite number of individual structural cells with brick shape. Each individual cell is the smallest representative volume in the fibrous assembly.

In this model, the yarns were assumed to travel along the diagonals in a unit cell and were treated as rigid-jointed frame members. By treating a unit cell specifically as a 3-D space frame, a 3-D frame finite element technique may be employed for the mechanistic analysis. A detailed description of the development of the FCM has been reported elsewhere [4,5].

Applying the FCM to the 3-D hybrid composites, the elastic properties of 0° lay-in yarns within the unit cell were distributed, as shown in Figure 6, into four longitudinal matrix-bars. The resultant properties of the four composite bars are obtained by the rule of mixture for the lay-in yarns and matrix-bars. A detailed procedure for the above considerations has been described in reference [6].

In order to account for the nonlinear behavior of the metal matrix in the hybrid composite, a quasi-linear model [7] for the matrix was used. This quasi-linear (hyperbolic) function is given as

$$\sigma = \epsilon / (a + b\epsilon) \quad (5)$$

where σ = current stress
 ϵ = current strain

$a = 1 / E_0$, the reciprocal of initial modulus

$b = 1 / \sigma_u$, the reciprocal of ultimate strength

With the basic parameters in a unit cell, such as yarn elastic modulus, fiber volume fraction, yarn orientation and unit cell dimension fully characterized, the structural response of the composites can now be predicted. While the elastic response can be synthesized with the FCM, the failure stress of the predicted stress-strain curve is determined by applying the rule-of-mixture strength criterion. Accordingly, the entire stress-strain curve of the composite can be simulated for various geometric and material hybrid systems.

Figure 7 shows the experimental and predicted stress-strain curves for the 100% Nicalon, 75% Nicalon/25% SCS-6 and 50% Nicalon/50% SCS-6 composites. Good agreement is shown between the experimental results and the predictions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study shows that a strong and tough MMC can be produced by geometric and material hybrids, combining large diameter filaments in a 3-D fiber network. Supported by experimental observations of the behavior of 3-D braided hybrid MMC under tensile, three point bending and compact tension tests, it can be seen that strong longitudinal-embedded fibers not only make the composites stronger and stiffer but also plays a vital role in modifying the failure mode of the composite.

In tensile tests, the dominant failure mode for the 100% Nicalon braided composites was matrix cracking, resulting in a smooth fracture surface. For the 50% Nicalon braided/50% SCS-6 lay-in composites, the SCS-6 filaments carry the load when both matrix and braiding yarns fail. The SCS-6 filaments alter the crack path and bridge the crack until the composite fails. A transition failure mode is observed for the 75% Nicalon braided/25% SCS-6 lay-in composites, wherein the composite was further toughened by fiber pull-out and crack deflection.

The fracture behavior of the composites was studied through three-point notched beam bending and compact tension tests. In the three-point bending tests, the strong SCS-6 filaments played a significant role in modifying the fracture behavior and preventing catastrophic failure of the composite. As more SCS-6 filaments were included, the composite fracture surfaces became rougher and showed an increasing degree of SCS-6 filament pull-out. The energy needed to induce failure increases as the percentage of SCS-6 filaments increases.

The compact tension tests demonstrated that the fracture surface energy of the composite decreases as the percentage of SCS-6 filaments increases as a result of stress concentration around the crack. The stress concentration effect becomes greater as the percentage of SCS-6 filaments increases. For braided hybrid specimens having notches perpendicular to the braiding axis, the strong SCS-6 filaments stop the crack growth and convert a mode-I failure into a boxed-mode failure. The fracture load of specimens with notch perpendicular to the braiding axis is higher than that of corresponding specimen with notch parallel to the braiding axis.

Modelling of the strength and stress-strain relationships of the composites was carried out based on a rule-of-mixture for hybrid composites and the FCM. The rule-of-mixture strength prediction agrees well with the experimental results. The FCM was shown to be capable of simulating the behavior of a hybrid composite when incorporated with the hyperbolic stress-strain relationships of the matrix.

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Table 1. Properties of the Fibers and Matrix

	Nicalon	SCS monofilament	Al 6061
Filament Diameter (μm)	10-15	140-142	
Cross section	round	round	
Filaments, yarn	500		
Count, tex	200		
Density, g/cm^3	2.55	3.0	2.7
Strength, GPa		3.4-4.5	
@ 20°C, as produced	2		
@ 1400°C in argon	<1.0		
@ 1400°C in oxygen	<0.5		
Tensile modulus, GPa	26	428	70
Creep strain @ 1300° C, 0.6 GPa, 20h%	4.5		
Coefficient of thermal expansion x 10^{-6} per °C	3.1	4.8	23

Table 2. Mechanical Properties of MMC

Nicalon/SCS-6	Ultimate Strength (MPa)		Initial Modulus (GPa)	
	Experimental	Predicted	Experimental	Predicted
100/0	121.4	128.8	88.28	91
75/25	256.9	253.8	95.6	97.45
50/50	599.2	603.5	102.6	113.4

Table 3. Fracture toughness of 3-D Braided Hybrid MMC

Nicalon/SCS-6	K_q ($\text{MPa} \cdot \sqrt{\text{m}}$)	K_{max} ($\text{MPa} \cdot \sqrt{\text{m}}$)
100/0	7.33	11.5
75/25	6.39	10.09
50/50	4.94	7.0

* Note : $1 \text{ MPa} \sqrt{\text{m}} = 0.9 \text{ Ksi} \sqrt{\text{in}}$

Figure 1. Schematic of a chevron-notched specimen and a compact tension specimen.

Figure 2. Experimental Results of hybrid MMC

Figure 3. Fracture Surface of Hybrid MMC under tensile load.

Figure 4. Schematic of load vs. deflection curves for a 3- pint bending fracture test.

Figure 5. Fracture energy of notched beams under 3-point bend

Figure 6. Unit Cell of Hybrid Structure

Figure 7. Tensile Stress-Strain Curves of 3-D Braid Hybrid MMC